

Studies on Hydrated Stannic Oxide as Anion-Exchanger : Part II. Distribution Coefficient Measurement, Elution Behaviour and Selective Ion Exchange Separation of Some Anions

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Distribution coefficients of anions on hydrated stannic oxide exchanger were determined at $pH < 2$ and > 4 . Elution behaviour of the anions on hydrated stannic oxide with different eluants were studied. On the basis of the distribution coefficients and elution study the specific separation of phosphate from chromate, arsenate, arsenite, thiocyanate, ferricyanide, ferrocyanide and vanadate has been achieved. Separations of thiocyanate from ferricyanide, ferrocyanide, chromate and arsenite; vanadate from chromate; arsenate from chromate, ferricyanide and arsenite have also become satisfactory. Chromate, was eluted either with 2.5(N) HCl or with 0.1(N) NaOH; arsenate and vanadate either with 2(N) HCl or with 2(N) HClO₄, arsenite with 5(N) HCl + C₂H₅OH = 2 : 3 (Vol/Vol), thiocyanate with 20% CH₃COOH + C₄H₉OH + CH₃COCH₃ = 2 : 2 : 1 (Vol/Vol), ferricyanide and ferrocyanide with 2(N) H₂SO₄. Phosphate was then eluted with 4(N) H₂SO₄.

IN this work hydrated stannic oxide batch 1 and 2 described in Part I¹ have been used in the measurement of the distribution coefficients of various anions and batch 1 only has been used in the elution study of various anions. Since batch 1, when dried at $(60 \pm 5)^\circ$, is more chemically stable in hydrochloric acid than the other batches. It is used in column operation. Very little quantitative work on the anion-exchange properties of hydrated stannic oxide has been reported^{2,3}. On the basis of these measurements selective ion-exchange separation of phosphate from chromate, arsenate, arsenite, thiocyanide, ferricyanide, ferrocyanide and vanadate from their binary mixtures have ferrocyanide been achieved. Satisfactory separation of thiocyanate from ferricyanide, ferrocyanide, chromate and arsenite; vanadate from chromate; arsenate from chromate, ferricyanide and arsenite have been achieved.

Experimental

Apparatus : For column operation 10 g of hydrated stannic oxide (batch 1 or 2 as the case may be) were inserted in a glass column (length 6.5 cm. I.D = 1.3 cm) with a glass wool support. The column was washed with demineralised water. The flow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min.

Distribution coefficients (K_d): The distribution coefficients of the anions were determined by batch operation at $pH < 2$ and $pH > 4$ with 500 mg amount of exchanger (batch 1 and 2). 50 ml of the anion solution was shaken for 40 hrs. at $(30 \pm 2)^\circ$. The anion concentration was kept at $4.3 \times 10^{-3} M$. pH of the solution was maintained at < 2 by nitric acid in all the cases except for ferrocyanide, arsenite and permanganate where it was made by sulphuric acid. The results are shown in Table-1. The K_d values of

TABLE-1. DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF ANIONS ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE (BATCH 1 AND 2) AT $(30 \pm 2)^\circ$.

Anions	K_d values at $pH < 2$		K_d values at $pH > 4$	
	Batch 1	Batch 2	Batch 1	Batch 2
CrO ₄ ²⁻	213.0	157.1	2.8	0.3
VO ₃ ⁻	281.0	1679.9	23.0	45.9
Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻	35.0	56.0	23.0	15.0
Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻	10.2	7.1	3.1	0.8
SCN ⁻	23.7	26.3	15.7	8.8
AsO ₄ ³⁻	208.7	707.2	8.6	6.8
AsO ₃ ³⁻	601.0	1302.0	601.0	218.0
PO ₄ ³⁻	58314.0	1700.0	354.2	205.0
MnO ₄ ⁻	2.5	8.5	0.5	0.5

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the a anions were also determined using different solvent systems with anion concentration of $(4.3-5.0) \times 10^{-3}M$ and the results are given in Table-2. Shaking period was 40 hrs. in all cases, except for ferrocyanide in which it was kept at 4 hrs. to avoid arial oxidation. Phosphate and molybdate were determined spectrophotometrically⁴ and all other anions were determined either volumetrically⁵ or gravimetrically⁴.

Elution behaviour of different anions :

On the basis of the results obtained by distribution study with different solvent systems the elution study of some anions was performed with different eluants using batch 1 exchanger. A known amount of anion was introduced into the column and the anion was eluted with different eluants. The results are shown in Table-3.

TABLE—2. DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF ANIONS ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE (BATCH 1) WITH DIFFERENT ELUANTS AT $(30 \pm 2)^\circ$

Solvent (eluant)	CrO ₂ ⁻	VO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ⁻	AsO ₄ ⁻	AsO ₃ ⁻	SCN ⁻	Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻	Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻
0.1 N HCl	166.5	96.36	1991.0	73.38	661.0	6.69	29.07	17.08
1.0 N HCl	29.8	20.57	109.6	68.66	310.8	-	23.0	4.36
2.0 N HCl	16.9	6.34	75.5	57.95	211.2	-	15.77	4.07
2.5 N HCl	11.2	4.46	50.3	44.99	185.3	-	-	-
2 N HCl : C ₂ H ₅ OH = 1 : 1 (Vol/Vol)	-	102.2	90.0	-	440.8	-	-	-
3 N HCl : C ₂ H ₅ OH = 1 : 3 (Vol/Vol)	28.3	70.69	90.0	-	562.6	-	-	-
5 N HCl : C ₂ H ₅ OH = 1 : 4 (Vol/Vol)	6.9	47.97	57.2	-	608.8	-	-	-
5 N HCl : C ₂ H ₅ OH = 2 : 3 (Vol/Vol)	-	-	50.0	-	38.4	-	-	-
0.1 N H ₂ SO ₄	13.43	347.3	636.0	73.38	222.0	-	18.33	9.48
1.0 N H ₂ SO ₄	10.0	21.13	144.0	59.3	163.3	-	15.2	6.7
2.0 N H ₂ SO ₄	5.4	15.8	90.1	50.3	105.4	-	6.5	4.1
3.0 N H ₂ SO ₄	3.2	10.8	42.0	35.5	86.8	-	-	2.8
0.01 N H ₂ O ₂	1158.6	4224.0	40736.0	-	-	-	-	-
1.0 N HNO ₃	2081.6	63.1	583140.0	-	-	-	-	-
2.0 N HNO ₃	1825.0	53.2	Total	-	-	-	-	-
			adsorption					
3.0 N HNO ₃	862.5	45.6	Total	-	-	-	-	-
			adsorption					
0.1 N HClO ₄	184.5	117.9	1716.0	-	413.5	-	-	23.2
1.0 N HClO ₄	361.0	44.0	14766.0	-	455.2	-	-	30.6
2.0 N HClO ₄	454.6	36.4	1262.0	-	927.0	-	-	39.3
20% CH ₃ COOH	38.0	-	1262.0	226.2	721.8	-	-	7.6
20% CH ₃ COOH : C ₂ H ₅ OH = 4 : 1 (Vol/Vol)	8.36	-	3988.0	195.3	542.1	-	-	4.9
20% CH ₃ COOH : C ₂ H ₅ OH = 2 : 3 (Vol/Vol)	5.9	-	1758.0	163.7	6750.0	-	-	-
20% CH ₃ COOH : nC ₄ H ₉ OH : CH ₃ COCH ₃ = 2 : 2 : 1 (Vol/Vol)	-	-	50.0	359.2	-	8.6	-	79.3

TABLE—3. ELUTION STUDIES OF DIFFERENT ANIONS ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE (BATCH 1) AT $(30 \pm 2)^\circ$.

Sl. No.	Ions	Solvent system	Length of the Column = 6.5 cm. Internal diameter = 1.3 cm.	Exchanger Rate	= 10 gms. = 1 ml/minute		% eluted
					Volume of solvent (ml)	Amount of ion taken (mg)	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1	CrO ₂ ⁻	2.5 (N) HCl	300	5.196	5.156	99.24	
		3 (N) H ₂ SO ₄	180	5.196	5.142	98.96	
		2.0 (N) HClO ₄	300	5.196	0.00	0.00	
		0.1 (N) NaOH	220	5.196	5.189	99.88	
2	VO ₃ ⁻	2.0 (N) HCl	180	5.0.9	5.045	100.53	
		2.0 (N) HClO ₄	200	5.019	4.759	94.83	
3	AsO ₄ ⁻	2.0 (N) HCl	160	7.835	7.673	97.94	
		2.0 (N) HClO ₄	220	7.835	7.801	99.58	
4	AsO ₃ ⁻	2.0 (N) HCl	300	6.870	0.00	0.00	
		3.0 (N) H ₂ SO ₄	300	6.870	0.00	0.00	
		5 (N) HCl : C ₂ H ₅ OH = 2 : 3 (Vol/Vol)	300	6.870	6.544	95.26	
		4 (N) H ₂ SO ₄	200	2.115	2.083	98.50	
5	PO ₄ ⁻	2.5 (N) HCl	300	2.115	0.000	0.00	
		2 (N) HClO ₄	300	2.115	0.000	0.00	
		20% CH ₃ COOH : n-C ₄ H ₉ OH : CH ₃ COCH ₃ = 2 : 2 : 1 (Vol/Vol)	100	2.749	2.726	99.13	
6	SCN ⁻	2 (N) HCl	150	8.240	7.830	95.11	
		2 (N) HCl	140	7.626	7.584	99.41	
		2 (N) H ₂ SO ₄	180	7.626	7.541	98.86	
7	[Fe(CN) ₆] ³⁻	20% CH ₃ COOH : n-C ₄ H ₉ OH : CH ₃ COCH ₃ = 2 : 2 : 1 (Vol/Vol)	300	7.626	0.000	0.00	
		2 (N) HClO ₄	300	7.626	0.000	0.00	
		2 (N) H ₂ SO ₄	160	3.604	3.303	98.65	
		20% CH ₃ COOH : n-C ₄ H ₉ OH : CH ₃ COCH ₃ = 2 : 2 : 1 (Vol/Vol)	300	3.604	0.000	0.00	

Results and Discussion

The method of preparation of inorganic ion-exchangers has a considerable effect on their degree of hydration and the composition of the sample. The factors are responsible for the shape and size of the cavities inside the exchanger and other properties of the exchanger⁶. Hydrated stannic oxide shows various degree of hydration and polymerization under different conditions. From Table-1 and 2 it is seen that distribution coefficients of phosphate, arsenate, arsenite, chromate and vanadate are very high and the K_a values of the anions decrease with increase of pH. This is in agreement with the fact that anion exchange capacity of hydrated stannic oxide decreases with increase of pH¹. In the elution

study it has been observed (Table-3) that vanadate is adsorbed by the exchanger forming a yellow band which can be easily eluted by hydrochloric acid or perchloric acid. It is interesting to note that chromate, phosphate and ferricyanide are strongly adsorbed by the exchanger in the presence of perchloric acid while vanadate is easily eluted with perchloric acid. It is also evident from the K_a values of those anions (Table-2). Another interesting point was noted that when the exchanger (batch 1) was dried at 70° to 80° for 1 hr vanadate was adsorbed very little by the exchanger and was eluted quantitatively with 50 ml. of water only, while chromate still remained adsorbed quantitatively by the exchanger and thus separated from vanadate.

Fig. 1. Separation of $CrO_4^{2-}-PO_4^{3-}$, $[AsO_4^{3-}]$, $SCN^- - PO_4^{3-}$, $[PO_4^{3-}Fe(CN)_6]^{3-} - PO_4^{3-}$, $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-} - PO_4^{3-}$, $VO_3^- - PO_4^{3-}$ on a hydrated oxide (Batch 1) column (I.D. 1.3cm). Flow rate 1 ml/min.

The plots of elution curves of some anions separated from each other in their binary mixtures are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3.

On the basis of the K_d values in Table-1 and 2 and elution study some quantitative separation of chromate, phosphate, thiocyanate, ferrocyanide, ferricyanide, vanadate, arsenate and arsenite have been achieved from their binary mixtures.

Fig. 1 shows that phosphate is selectively separated from chromate, arsenate, arsenite, thiocyanate, ferricyanide, ferrocyanide and vanadate. Thiocyanate is selectively separated (Fig. 2) from ferrocyanide,

ferricyanide, chromate and arsenite (Table 4). Besides, the following quantitative binary separations (Fig. 3) have been achieved: vanadate from chromate, arsenate from chromate, arsenate from ferricyanide, and arsenate from arsenite.

It was observed later on that when batch 2 was heated to 300° it could withstand the chemical action of more concentrated eluants and some binary separation of anions have been achieved efficiently with smaller eluant volume. Hence batch 2 may be used more effectively for anion separation particularly at high temperature. The exchanger has also a good regeneration capacity.

Fig. 2. Separation of SCN^- — $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, SCN^- — $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ on a hydrated stannic oxide (Batch 1) column (I.D. 1.3 cm. Flow rate, 1 ml/min.

TABLE-4. SEPARATION OF THIOCYANATE FROM OTHER ANIONS ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE (BATCH 1) COLUMNS AT $(30 \pm 2)^\circ$

Sl. No.	Mixture separated	Eluent	Volume of Eluant (ml.)	Taken in mg.	Found in mg.	Error (%)
1	Thiocyanate	20% CH_3COOH : $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$: $\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3 = 2 : 2 : 1$ (Vol/Vol)	160	6.48	5.45	-0.54
	Ferrocyanide	3 (N) H_2SO_4	160	8.05	7.97	-0.99
2	Thiocyanate	20% CH_3COOH : $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$: $\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3 = 2 : 2 : 1$ (Vol/Vol)	160	5.48	5.45	-0.54
	Ferricyanide	2 (N) HCl	160	7.63	7.56	-0.91
3	Thiocyanate	0.5 (N) HCl	200	8.24	7.93	-3.70
	Chromate	2.5 (N) HCl	300	6.49	6.46	-0.46
4	Thiocyanate	1.0 (N) HCl	150	7.77	7.48	-3.70
	Arsenite	5 (N) HCl : $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} = 2 : 3$ (Vol/Vol)	300	4.71	4.62	-1.90

Fig. 3. Separation of VO_3^- - CrO_4^{2-} , AsO_4^{3-} - CrO_4^{2-} , AsO_4^{3-} [$-\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$] $^{3-}$, AsO_4^{3-} - AsO_3^{3-} on a hydrated stannic oxide (Batch 1) column (I.D. 1.3 cm.) Flow rate, 1 ml/min.

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